

QUANTIFICATION AND VALIDATION OF WIDE GENETIC FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH ADAPTATION AND YIELD IN KAZAKH WHEATS

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Wheat is a strategic crop globally, with immense importance in Central Asia. Kazakhstan, known for its high-quality wheat grain, plays a pivotal role as a key wheat supplier both regionally and internationally. The country significantly contributes to regional and global food security, exporting approximately half of its wheat production, amounting to 6–8 million tons annually. However, local wheat breeding practices in Kazakhstan predominantly rely on traditional methods. Thus, the genetic control of yield related traits is poorly understood. To meet the challenges posed by rapid climate change, it is essential to accelerate breeding processes, focusing on developing high-quality varieties resilient to both abiotic and biotic stress factors. To support this effort, we have employed systematic plant breeding techniques coupled with modern technologies, mapping a wide array of genetic factors associated with key economic traits in Kazakhstani wheat through our advanced genetic strategies. For example, high-resolution genetic mapping and validation of height-controlling genes on the 5A and 6A chromosomes—predominant in Kazakh wheat—have shown limited benefits in terms of yield and quality across several wheat-growing environments. This suggests the need to breed for alternative alleles at these loci. Currently, Near Isogenic Lines (NILs) carrying "short" alleles are being developed in the genetic background of Kazakh wheat. Additionally, QTL mapping of coleoptile architecture across four mapping populations, derived from crosses between four Kazakh elite wheat cultivars and a single UK wheat reference, revealed that local germplasm is largely fixed for key adaptation and yield-related traits but although remains diverse for other loci.